

Thermo-Osmosis and Higher Order Symmetries*

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An attempt has been made to obtain a non-linear phenomenological relation between fluxes and forces for the mass transport of matter and the transport of heat energy in thermo-osmosis as viewed from the physical parameters of the classical theory. Poiseuillean flow for fluids (liquids and gases) through membrane capillaries has been taken into consideration for such an attempt. Occurrences of higher order symmetries have also been examined and observed in the present study.

IN continuation of our earlier studies^{1,2} for higher order symmetries³⁻⁷, we now examine thermo-osmosis. Known physical parameters of classical theory has been used as a tool. Some such attempt has been made earlier by Rastogi and others^{8(a)} for the Knudsen flow of gases through membrane capillaries. Our line of approach is, however, entirely different. It deals with the Poiseuillean flow of matter, a fluid (liquid or gas), through the membrane capillaries and the flow of thermal energy by two methods: Convection and Conduction.

For any Markoffian† process, the local fluxes J_i are the functions of local forces X_i , the intensive parameters a_i and the structural factor G . Hence,

$$J_i = f(X_1, X_2, \dots, a_1, a_2, \dots, G).$$

G is a factor which takes into account the characteristics of the system. For illustration we may consider fluid flow through a capillary or a tube. The flow depends upon the temperature, T , pressure, P , pressure difference, ΔP and temperature difference, ΔT . In addition, the flow depends on structural factor, G , which is a function of the length and diameter of the capillary.

The basic foundation of the thermodynamics of irreversible processes^{9,10}, is Gibb's equation, linear phenomenological law and the Onsager's reciprocity relations. The domain of validity of linear laws is smaller as compared to that of the Gibb's equation for entropy production provided the non-linear form of the phenomenological equation can be determined^{1,5(b)}. Progress in statistical mechanics^{11,12} is still limited and does not yet permit the formal development of a microscopic thermodynamic theory in the non-linear range. The present communication is an attempt to obtain a non-linear phenomenological equation for thermo-osmosis of a fluid (liquid or gas) for the Poiseuillean flow.

The thermodynamic theory of irreversible processes⁹⁻¹⁰ gives^{10,13} the following rate-equation for thermo-osmosis of a fluid (liquid or gas) in the linear range

$$J_M = L'_{11}(-v\Delta P'/T) + L'_{12}(-\Delta T/T^2) \quad \dots (1)$$

$$H = L'_{21}(-v\Delta P'/T) + L'_{22}(-\Delta T/T^2) \quad \dots (2)$$

where J_M , H , $\Delta P'$ and ΔT , respectively stand for mass flow of matter, thermal flow of energy (commonly known as heat flow), the observed solvodynamic pressure difference and temperature difference respectively, acting as the driving forces across a membrane. T is the mean temperature of the two compartments I and II, in the Kelvin scale, v is the specific volume of the fluid concerned and L'^s signify the rate coefficients^{10,13}. At a constant mean temperature, T , the above equations may be simplified as

$$J_M = L_{11}(\Delta P') + L_{12}(\Delta T) \quad \dots (3)$$

$$H = L_{21}(\Delta P') + L_{22}(\Delta T) \quad \dots (4)$$

where $L_{12} (= -L'_{12}/T^2)$ is known as thermo-osmotic permeability of the permeant at the mean temperature T due to the coupling effect.

Classical theory relates L_{11} and L_{22} to the physical parameters of the system through Poiseuille's and Fourier's equations respectively as given under:

$$L_{11} = n\pi r^4 \rho / 8\eta l \quad \dots (5)$$

$$L_{22} = K.n\pi r^2 / l = K.A/l \quad \dots (6)$$

in which ρ , n , η , r , l and K represent the density of the permeant at the mean temperature T , no. of capillaries available for permeation of the fluid

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† Markoffian system explained at the end.

through the membrane in question, the viscosity of the fluid at temperature T , the average radius¹, the average length¹ of the membrane capillaries and the heat conductivity coefficient respectively. A is the effective cross-sectional area of the membrane. Since K remains constant for an appreciable width of ΔT , L_{22} also behaves similarly at any fixed mean temperature.

In transport processes coupling leads to a decrease in straight coefficients^{1,14,15} when restrictions are imposed on fluxes. Thus in thermo-osmosis we obtain equation (8) through equation (7) in association with equation (3) i.e.,

$$(\Delta T)_{H=0} = (-L_{21}/L_{22})\Delta P' \quad \dots (7)$$

$$(J_M)_{H=0} = L_{11}(1 - L_{12}L_{21}/L_{11}L_{22})\Delta P' \quad \dots (8)$$

Likewise, we also obtain equation (10) through equation (9) in combination with equation (4)

$$(\Delta P')_{J_M=0} = (-L_{12}/L_{11})\Delta T \quad \dots (9)$$

$$(H)_{J_M=0} = L_{22}(1 - L_{21}L_{12}/L_{11}L_{22})\Delta T \quad \dots (10)$$

The quantities in the first parenthesis in the r.h.s. of equation (8) and (10) are the same, positive and less than unity. This is in conformity with the earlier observations^{1,14,15}.

The absence of either the matter flux or the thermal energy flux in thermo-osmosis is due to a nullifying effect for the generation of the flux of a particular kind by that due to the other because of the thermodynamic equivalence between the two¹. Thus in thermo-osmosis where the system comprises of two compartments I and II, maintained at two different but constant temperatures, T_1 and T_2 , ($T_2 > T_1$) respectively and apparently there is no flow of thermal energy from compartment II to compartment I although the flow of matter continues, it may be argued that the accompanying thermal energy of the outgoing matter from compartment II to compartment I is just counter-balanced by a reverse process of operation i.e. the thermo-mechanical effect, ΔT_{tms} (subscript tme stands for the abbreviation "thermo-mechanical effect")¹⁰ or mechano-caloric effect¹⁰, so that

$$\begin{array}{c} \longrightarrow \\ \Delta T_{tms} = \Delta T = \frac{L_{21}}{L_{22}} \Delta P' \end{array} \quad (11)$$

and therefore, the experimentally observed value for thermo-osmotic pressure, $\Delta P'$, developed in the system under such a situation, would apparently record a value which would be a little short of the real and net effective value operative in the system. Hence a part of the real thermo-osmotic pressure which is due to be observed in compartment I,

would thus be deemed to be consumed for restraining the temperature rise in it because of the associated thermal energy of the fluid entering in it from compartment II on account of the thermo-osmotic phenomenon. The actual and correct value of the real and net effective thermo-osmotic pressure, ΔP , may therefore, be supposed to be given by a quantity which incorporates the equivalent additive correction factor given by $K_1 \Delta T$ (where $K_1 = S \Delta T$ and S is the specific heat of the fluid at the mean temperature, T) in the observed value of $\Delta P'$ for it. Thus

$$\Delta P = \Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T \quad \dots (12)$$

One can arrive at the above conclusion from other considerations also. We will discuss this aspect a little later.

Poiseuillean flow of a fluid^{16,17} (liquid or gas) through a composite membrane consisting of n capillaries gives the following expression^{1,18} for the net effective pressure in terms of the rate solvodynamic permeation, J_M , as

$$\Delta P = (8\eta l/n\pi r^4 \rho) J_M + (1/n^2 \pi^2 r^4 \rho^2) J_M^2 \quad \dots (13)$$

where every symbol has its usual significance¹. J_M for the non-linear range is expressed¹ as

$$\begin{aligned} J_M &= \frac{n\pi r^4 \rho}{8\eta l} \Delta P \left(1 + \frac{r^4}{8^2 \eta^2 l^2} \Delta P\right)^{-1} \\ &= \frac{n\pi r^4 \rho}{8\eta l} \Delta P - \frac{n\pi r^8 \rho}{8^2 \eta^2 l^2} \Delta P^2 + \frac{n\pi r^{12} \rho}{8^3 \eta^3 l^3} \Delta P^3 \quad \dots (14) \end{aligned}$$

Equation (14), however, takes a little different appearance when the transport of a compressed gas is considered in vacuum or against a constant but negligible pressure through the capillaries under the condition such that $\lambda < r$, λ being the mean free path of the gas molecules at temperature T . The

boundary condition, i.e., \vec{u} (velocity of gas in any desired direction) at r , under such a situation is affected and a slip of the first molecular layer of the fluid at r of the capillary occurs^{17,19}. This situation presents the transition from Poiseuille's flow to Knudsen flow (where J_M is dependent^{17,19} on r^8).

[The slip flow expression differs from the true molecular flow (Knudsen flow) by a factor $3\pi/16$. No quantitative kinetic theory treatment of the flow in the transition region ($\lambda \approx r$) exists at present.] J_M under such condition also may, conveniently, be described by an expression in terms of the power series of ΔP . According to Present¹⁹

$$J_M = \frac{n\pi r^4}{8\eta R'Tl} \left(\frac{(\Delta P)^2}{2} + \frac{n\pi r^8}{\eta l} \Delta P \right) \quad \dots 14(a)$$

The average pressure, \bar{P} , under the above given condition may be approximately taken as equal to $\Delta P/2$. We will call this system as system 'B' while that of the general i.e., the previous one, as system 'A'. Rearrangement of equation 14(a) leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta P &= \frac{l\bar{v}}{n\pi r^3} \left(1 + \frac{r\bar{v}}{16\eta R'T} \Delta P\right)^{-1} \cdot J_M \\ &= \frac{l\bar{v}}{n\pi r^3} \left(1 - \frac{r\bar{v}}{16\eta R'T} \Delta P\right) J_M \end{aligned} \quad \dots 14(b)$$

wherefrom we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} J_M &= \frac{n\pi r^3}{l\bar{v}} \cdot \Delta P \left(1 - \frac{r\bar{v}}{16\eta R'T} \Delta P\right)^{-1} \\ &= \frac{n\pi r^3}{l\bar{v}} \Delta P + \frac{n\pi r^4}{16\eta R'T} \Delta P^2 + \frac{n\pi r^6 \bar{v}}{16^2 \eta^2 R'^2 T^2} \Delta P^3 \\ &+ \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots 14(c) \end{aligned}$$

In the above expressions, $R' (= R/M, R$ and M being the molar gas constant and the molecular weight of the gas respectively) is the gas constant per gram of the gas, and $\bar{v}^* [= (8KT/\pi m)^{1/2}]$ stands for the mean speed of the molecules at the mean temperature, T . It may be noted that L_{11} for J_M in the present situation becomes dependent¹⁹ on r^3 in this slip flow region as against r^4 in the general Poiseuillean equation^{17,19}.

Remembering that the effective thermo-osmotic pressure, ΔP , is governed by equation (12) for a fluid permeation, the correct expression for J_M , in terms of the power series of its driving force, $(\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T)$, viz. the observed thermo-osmotic pressure, and the temperature difference of the system, is given under.

$$\begin{aligned} J_M &= \frac{n\pi r^4 \rho}{8\eta l} (\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T) - \frac{n\pi r^6 \rho}{8^2 \eta^2 l^3} (\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T)^2 \\ &+ \frac{n\pi r^{12} \rho}{8^3 \eta^3 l^5} (\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T)^3 \end{aligned} \quad \dots (15)$$

which for the flow of a compressed gas against negligible pressure or in vacuum takes the form,

$$\begin{aligned} J_M &= \frac{n\pi r^3}{l\bar{v}} (\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T) + \frac{n\pi r^4}{16\eta R'T} (\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T)^2 \\ &+ \frac{n\pi r^6 \bar{v}}{16^2 \eta^2 R'^2 T^2} (\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T)^3 + \dots \dots 15(a) \end{aligned}$$

* The Maxwell-Boltzman equilibrium distribution function $f^{(0)}$ has been used for the derivation of the above equation, since it is sufficiently valid approximation for near equilibrium situations to which our system belongs. The number density of molecules is constant irrespective of the type of distribution^{8(a),20}

$$\int f c d c = \int f^{(0)} c d c$$

where f is the true distribution function and c is the velocity. Hence the average velocity of molecules is the same as in equilibrium provided the local temperature is not altered. As in earlier approaches of this kind,^{1,8,9(a)} the domain of the validity of Gibbs' equation has been assumed to hold in the present case also. This is also in conformity with the ideas advanced by Prigogine²¹.

Considering now the transfer of thermal energy in the system we find that the total flow of heat energy from compartment II at T_2 to compartment I at T_1 may be supposed to be given by a sum of two factors arising out of two separate contributions: (a) that due to convection on account of thermo-osmosis of the fluid from compartment II at T_2 to compartment I at T_1 ($T_2 > T_1$) i.e. $J_1 S \Delta T$, where $S (= C_v$ in the case of a compressed gas) is the specific heat of the fluid at the mean temperature T and (b) that due to conduction i.e. J_2 given by the quantity $K.n\pi r^2/l$. The net flow of heat energy in the system from compartment at T_2 to that at T_1 in the linear range, therefore, may be written as,

$$H = J_1 S \Delta T + J_2 (= K.n\pi r^2 \Delta T/l) \quad \dots (16)$$

Before attempting to obtain a non-linear expression for heat flow we would like to add that the two fluxes, viz. the mass flow and the heat flow, in the present context may, conveniently, be described by the equalities,

$$J_M = J_1 + O J_2 \quad \dots (17)$$

$$H = K_1 J_1 + J_2 \quad \dots (18)$$

In the above equations J_1 is the mass flow due to the observed thermo-osmotic pressure i.e., $\Delta P'$ and J_2 is the heat flow due to conduction. The first term in the r.h.s. of equation (18) refers to the flow of thermal energy by convection.

The entropy production, ϕ , for the system, described by

$$\phi = \sum J_i X_i = J \Delta P' + H \Delta T \quad \dots (19)$$

may, in the light of equations (17) and (18), be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \phi &= J_1 \Delta P' + (K_1 J_1 + J_2) \Delta T \\ &= J_1 \Delta P' + K_1 J_1 \Delta T + J_2 \Delta T \\ &= J_1 (\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T) + J_2 \Delta T \end{aligned} \quad \dots (20)$$

In equation (20) we find the new force for solvodynamic permeation to be given by $(\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T)$ i.e., the net total effective pressure as envisaged in our equation (12).

To obtain the non-linear range, in terms of L_1^s Taylor type expansion in power series of ΔT and $\Delta P'$ we replace J_1 in the 1st term of the right-hand side of equation (16) by its expression in the power series of $\Delta P'$ and ΔT given by equations (15) and 15(a) for thermo-osmotic flow of a fluid, respectively, for system A and system B. The expression for H , in terms of L^s whose meaning is given by the corresponding coefficients of the equivalent

powers of $(\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T)$ in equations (15) and 15(a), thus becomes²

$$H = K_1 \left[L_{111} (\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T) + \frac{1}{2!} L_{1111} (\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T)^2 + \frac{1}{3!} L_{11111} (\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T)^3 + \dots \dots \right] + L_{22} \Delta T$$

wherefrom on simplification and rearrangement we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} H &= K_1 L_{111} \Delta P' + (K_1^2 L_{111} + L_{22}) \Delta T \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} K_1 L_{1111} (\Delta P')^2 + K_1^2 L_{1111} (\Delta P') (\Delta T) \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} K_1^3 L_{1111} (\Delta T)^2 + \frac{1}{3!} K_1 L_{11111} (\Delta P')^3 \\ &+ \frac{1}{3!} \cdot 3 \cdot L_{11111} (\Delta P')^2 \Delta T K_1^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{3!} \cdot 3 \cdot L_{11111} \Delta P' (\Delta T)^2 K_1^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{3!} L_{11111} K_1^4 (\Delta T)^3 + \dots \quad (21) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly from equations (14) and 14(c) we get² J_M as

$$\begin{aligned} J_M &= J_1 [\text{cf. eqn. (17)}] \\ &= L_{11} (\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T) + \frac{1}{2!} L_{111} (\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T)^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{3!} L_{1111} (\Delta P' + K_1 \Delta T)^3 + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Proper arrangement of which in terms of $\Delta P'$ and ΔT gives,

$$\begin{aligned} J_M &= L_{11} \Delta P' + K_1 L_{111} \Delta T \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} L_{1111} (\Delta P')^2 + L_{1111} K_1 \Delta P' \Delta T \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} L_{1111} K_1^2 (\Delta T)^2 + \frac{1}{3!} L_{11111} (\Delta P')^3 \\ &+ \frac{1}{3!} \cdot 3 \cdot L_{11111} (\Delta P')^2 \Delta T K_1 \\ &+ \frac{1}{3!} \cdot 3 \cdot L_{11111} \Delta P' (\Delta T)^2 K_1^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{3!} L_{11111} (\Delta T)^3 K_1^3 + \dots \quad (22) \end{aligned}$$

If subscripts 1 and 2 associated with L^s are now recognised for the indication of matter flow and thermal energy (heat) flow respectively, as has been done in equations (3) and (4) earlier, then from equations (21) and (22) we obtain the following equalities, akin to those of electro-kinetics, with parametric equations in terms of L^s as used in the steady state thermodynamics^{9,10}.

System 'A'

$$\begin{aligned} L_{21} &= K_1 L_{11} = K_1 \cdot n \pi r^4 \rho / 8 \eta l = L_{12} \\ 2L_{211} &= K_1 L_{111} = K_1 \cdot 2! n \pi r^5 \rho / 8^2 \eta^2 l^2 = L_{112} \\ L_{212} &= K_1^2 L_{111} = K_1^2 \cdot 2! n \pi r^5 \rho / 8^2 \eta^2 l^2 = 2L_{122} \\ 3L_{2111} &= \frac{1}{2} K_1 L_{1111} = \frac{1}{2} K_1 \cdot 3! n \pi r^6 \rho / 8^3 \eta^3 l^3 \\ &= L_{1112} \\ L_{2122} &= \frac{1}{2} K_1^2 L_{1111} = \frac{1}{2} K_1^2 \cdot 3! n \pi r^6 \rho / 8^3 \eta^3 l^3 \\ &= 3L_{1222} \quad \dots \quad (23) \end{aligned}$$

System 'B'

$$\begin{aligned} L_{21} &= K_1 L_{11} = K_1 \cdot n \pi r^4 / l \bar{v} = L_{12} \\ 2L_{211} &= K_1 L_{111} = K_1 \cdot 2! n \pi r^4 / 16 \eta R' T l = L_{112} \\ L_{212} &= K_1^2 L_{111} = K_1^2 \cdot 2! n \pi r^4 / 16 \eta R' T l = 2L_{122} \\ 3L_{2111} &= \frac{1}{2} K_1 L_{1111} = \frac{1}{2} K_1 \cdot 3! n \pi r^5 \bar{v} / 16^2 \eta^2 R'^2 T^2 l \\ &= L_{1112} \\ L_{2122} &= \frac{1}{2} K_1^2 L_{1111} = \frac{1}{2} K_1^2 \cdot 3! n \pi r^5 \bar{v} / 16^2 \eta^2 R'^2 T^2 l \\ &= 3L_{1222} \quad \dots \quad 23(a) \end{aligned}$$

In observing the above symmetries it has to be noted that the above equalities are obtained through the association of L_{11} , L_{111} and L_{1111} , etc. with K_1 ($= S \Delta T$, S being the specific heat of a liquid at the mean temperature T , in case of a gas it is taken as C_v) which we have assumed to be a constant quantity. But K_1 is constant only when ΔT is kept unaltered at the constant mean temperature T . The temperature difference ΔT , between the two chambers under consideration may, however, be conveniently varied without in any way affecting the fixed mean temperature T . It is, therefore, of interest to investigate the impact of the variation of ΔT (between the two chambers, keeping the mean temperature, T unaltered) on the L^s and the equalities. For this K_1 ($= S \Delta T$ or $C_v \Delta T$) of equations (21) and (22) is replaced by $S \cdot \Delta T$. This leads to equations (24) and (25). The factor ΔT in K_1 ($= S \Delta T$), which was dormant and non-operative as a force in equations (21) and (22), associates itself with the operative part of the force as ΔT in the system and thereby reshapes equations (21) and (22) as given in equations (24) and (25) respectively.

$$\begin{aligned}
 H = & SL_{11}(\Delta P')(\Delta T) + S^2 L_{11}(\Delta T)^2 + L_{22} \Delta T \\
 & + \frac{1}{2!} L_{111} S(\Delta P')^2(\Delta T) + S^2 L_{111}(\Delta P')(\Delta T)^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{2!} S^2 L_{111}(\Delta T)^2 + \frac{1}{3!} L_{1111} S(\Delta P')^3(\Delta T) \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} 3L_{1111} S^2(\Delta P')^2(\Delta T)^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} 3L_{1111} S^3(\Delta P')(\Delta T)^3 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} L_{1111} S^4(\Delta T)^4 + \dots \quad \dots (24)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_M = & L_{11}(\Delta P') + L_{11} S(\Delta T)^2 + \frac{1}{2!} L_{111}(\Delta P')^2 \\
 & + L_{111} S(\Delta P')(\Delta T)^2 + \frac{1}{2!} L_{1111} S^2(\Delta T)^4 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} L_{1111}(\Delta P')^3 + \frac{1}{3!} 3L_{1111} S(\Delta P')^2(\Delta T)^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} 3L_{1111} S^2 \Delta P'(\Delta T)^3 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} L_{1111} S^3(\Delta T)^6 + \dots \quad \dots (25)
 \end{aligned}$$

Equations (24) and (25) may be rearranged in a proper sequence of ΔP and ΔT which, when rewritten in the conventional L_i^s Taylor type expansion form, appear as given in equations (26) and (27).

$$\begin{aligned}
 H = & L_{212}^* \Delta P' \Delta T + L_{2222}^* (\Delta T)^2 + L_{22}^* \Delta T \\
 & + \frac{1}{2!} L_{2112}^* (\Delta P')^2 \Delta T + L_{21222}^* \Delta P' (\Delta T)^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{2!} L_{222222}^* (\Delta T)^2 + \frac{1}{3!} L_{21112}^* (\Delta P')^3 \Delta T \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} L_{211222}^* (\Delta P')^2 (\Delta T)^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} L_{2122222}^* \Delta P' (\Delta T)^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} L_{22222222}^* (\Delta T)^7 + \dots \quad \dots (26)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_M = & L_{11}^* \Delta P' + L_{122}^* (\Delta T)^2 + \frac{1}{2!} L_{111}^* (\Delta P')^2 \\
 & + L_{1122}^* \Delta P' (\Delta T)^2 + \frac{1}{2!} L_{12222}^* (\Delta T)^4 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} L_{1111}^* (\Delta P')^3 + \frac{1}{3!} L_{11122}^* (\Delta P')^2 \Delta T^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} L_{112222}^* \Delta P' (\Delta T)^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} L_{12222222}^* (\Delta T)^6 + \dots \quad (27)
 \end{aligned}$$

Adopting now the same procedure, as observed earlier, for examining the obedience of the higher

order symmetries one again obtains the equalities shown in (28) and 28(a) through the same set of parameters. Thus we have for

System 'A'

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{212}^* &= S \cdot L_{11} = S \cdot n\pi r^4 \rho / 8\eta l = L_{122}^* \\
 2L_{2112}^* &= S \cdot L_{111} = S \cdot 2! n\pi r^3 \rho / 8^2 \eta^2 l^2 = L_{1122}^* \\
 L_{21222}^* &= S^2 \cdot L_{1111} = S^2 \cdot 2! n\pi r^2 \rho / 8^3 \eta^3 l^3 = 2L_{12222}^* \\
 3L_{21112}^* &= \frac{1}{2} S \cdot L_{11111} = \frac{1}{2} S \cdot 3! n\pi r^2 \rho / 8^2 \eta^2 l^2 \\
 &= L_{11112}^* \\
 L_{2122222}^* &= \frac{1}{2} S^2 \cdot L_{111111} = \frac{1}{2} S^2 \cdot 3! n\pi r^2 \rho / 8^2 \eta^2 l^2 \\
 &= 3L_{1222222}^* \quad \dots (28)
 \end{aligned}$$

System 'B'

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{212}^* &= C_v (=S) \cdot L_{11} = C_v \cdot n\pi r^2 / \bar{v} = L_{122}^* \\
 2L_{2112}^* &= C_v \cdot L_{111} = C_v \cdot 2! n\pi r^4 / 16\eta R'Tl = L_{1122}^* \\
 L_{21222}^* &= C_v^2 \cdot L_{1111} = C_v^2 \cdot 2! n\pi r^4 / 16\eta R'Tl \\
 &= 2L_{12222}^* \\
 3L_{21112}^* &= \frac{1}{2} C_v \cdot L_{11111} = \frac{1}{2} C_v \cdot 3! n\pi r^5 \bar{v} / 16^2 \eta^2 R'^2 T^2 l \\
 &= L_{11112}^* \\
 L_{2122222}^* &= \frac{1}{2} C_v^2 \cdot L_{111111} = \frac{1}{2} C_v^2 \cdot 3! n\pi r^5 \bar{v} / \\
 &16^2 \eta^2 R'^2 T^2 l = 3L_{1222222}^* \quad 28(a)
 \end{aligned}$$

As pointed out earlier the values of the L^s with identical superscripts in the equalities shown in equation (23) differ in set and magnitude of the parameters from that shown in equation (28). Similar is the case with the equalities shown in equations 23(a) and 28(a) also. The difference as will be observed, is very symmetrical and is accounted for the fact discussed in earlier pages. If we look into their interrelationship we find that the equalities of equations (23) and 23(a) i.e., $L_{21} = L_{12}$, $2L_{211} = L_{112}$ and $L_{212} = 2L_{122}$ etc. become correspondingly, equal to the equalities, $L_{212}^* = L_{122}^*$, $2L_{2112}^* = L_{1122}^*$ and $L_{21222}^* = 2L_{12222}^*$ etc. of equations (28) and 28(a) respectively with the same and identical parametric values on account of the fact discussed subsequently after equation 23(a).

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References

1. K. M. JHA, Md. ZAKARIA and S. P. JHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 745.

* The superscript * in the above equations and equalities has been used only to differentiate the L^s in these with those of the previous ones.

2. K. M. JHA and Md. ZAKARIA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 598.
3. J. C. M. LI, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1958, **29**, 747.
4. J. C. M. LI, *J. Appl. Physics*, 1962, **33**, 616.
5. R. P. RASTOGI, R. C. SRIVASTAVA and K. SINGH, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1965, **61**, 854.
6. K. M. JHA and Md. ZAKARIA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 366.
7. K. M. JHA and Md. ZAKARIA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 339.
8. (a) R. P. RASTOGI and K. SINGH, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, **63**, 2917.
(b) R. P. RASTOGI and R. C. SRIVASTAVA, *Physica*, 1961, **27**, 265.
9. I. PRIGOGINE, "Introduction to Thermodynamics of Irreversible Processes." Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1967.
10. S. R. DE GROOT, "Thermodynamics of Irreversible Processes." North-Holland Publishing Company, Amsterdam, 1966.
11. R. EISENSCHITZ, "Statistical Theory of Irreversible Process", Oxford University Press, 1958.
12. J. G. KIRKWOOD and R. J. BEARMAN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1958, **28**, 136.
13. R. P. RASTOGI, R. L. BLOKHRA and R. K. AGARWAL, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1964, **60**, 1386.
14. O. KEDEM and A. KATCHALSKY, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, **59**, 1918.
15. N. LAKSHMINARAYANAIAH, "Transport Phenomena in Membrane", Academic Press, New York and London, 1969.
16. F. H. NEWMAN and G. F. C. SEARLE, "The General Properties of Matter", Edward Arnold Publishers Ltd., London, 1957, Chapter VII.
17. L. B. LOEB, "The Kinetic Theory of Gases", Dover Publications, Inc., New York, 1961, 3rd Edn.
18. F. DANIELS, J. WILLIAMS, P. BENDER, R. ALBERTY and C. D. CORNWELL, "Experimental Physical Chemistry", Mc-Graw Hill Book Co. Inc., New York, 1962, Chapter VIII.
19. R. D. PRESENT, "Kinetic Theory of Gases", Mc-Graw Hill Book Co. Inc., New York, Toronto, London, 1958, Chapters III and IV.
20. S. Chapman and T. G. COWLING in Co-operation with D. BURNETT, "The Mathematical Theory of non-Uniform Gases." Third Edition, University Press, Cambridge, 1970, p. 112.
21. I. PRIGOGINE, *Physica*, 1949, **15**, 272.

Note : For Markoffian system, the fluxes at a given instant depend only on the value of affinity at that instant, for example a pure resistor, whereas a circuit with capacitance and inductance in which the fluxes may depend upon the values of the affinities at previous time as well as at that instant, is a non-Markoffian system.